

Ground Deformation in Nisyros Volcano (Greece) Determined by GPS and SAR Interferometric Techniques

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Introduction

The southeastern part of the Hellenic Volcanic Arc (HVA), including Kos, Yali and Nisyros islands, is geodynamically very active (Figure 1). Intense seismic activity occurred on Nisyros Island during 1996-1998, accompanied with strong ground deformation and temperature increase of the fumaroles. Nisyros Island lies above a basement of Mesozoic limestone (Geotermica Italiana 1983; 1984). The exposed rocks are Quaternary volcanics. The evolution of Nisyros Volcano during the past 160,000 years, together with the succession of calc-alkaline lavas and pyroclastic rocks, has been studied in detail by various authors (ie Hardimann 1999; Tibaldi et al. 2008).

Major fault systems have been identified within the volcanic edifices of the Kos-Yali-Nisyros Volcanic Field (Figure 1) on the basis of structural and geological investigations (ie Papanikolaou and Nomikou 2001; Nomikou and Papanikolaou 2011). The caldera's rim and its accompanying cone-shaped local faults are entirely volcanic structures, which are a result of the collapsing of the caldera after the last Plinian eruptions.

Figure 1. Left part: Distribution of stations of the GPS network of the Kos-Yali-Nisyros Volcanic Field. Solid red circles represent the two modelled Mogi point sources. Str stands for the station established on Strongyli Islet). Right part: Fault pattern of major faulting systems (F1 to F7), location of hydrothermal explosion craters and other significant features superimposed on a digital elevation model of Nisyros Island. Abbreviations of locations; PI: Prophitis Elias, Lp: Lakki Plain.

Earthquakes have been described throughout historical times as has been reported in detail since 1830 (Gorceix 1873a, b and c; Stiros and Vougioukalakis 1996). Their origin may be a result of regional tectonic processes, magma ascent, degassing phenomena of deep crustal magma and steam explosions within the hydrothermal system. The Mandraki Fault (Figure 1) that comprises a branch of the F3 fault system was reactivated in 1996 (Lagios et al. 2005) and caused damage

to buildings and other structures within Mandraki (Ioannidis 1998). Tectonic processes expressed by the latest seismicity indicate tensional fracturing (Makris and Chonia 1999) which could reduce the lithostatic pressure and trigger explosive volcanic phenomena, such as those reported in 1871 and 1873 by Gorceix (1873a). The most recent seismic activity in the area was in 2017 with a strong earthquake (Mw6.2; Jul. 20, 2017) taking place NE of Kos Island (Ganas et al., 2019). Moreover, increased seismicity occurred during Jun-August 2021, in the marine area SW of Nisyros. Both these bursts of seismicity were of tectonic character and have not been associated with volcanic activity.

Efforts for studying the ground deformation on Nisyros started after the outbreak of the seismic activity in 1996 and have involved GPS observations and SAR interferometric analysis (e.g. Lagios et al. 2005;). This study presents the ground deformation on Nisyros up to 2023 and addresses its evolution during the years 2002-2023 on the basis of combined GPS/GNSS and advanced SAR interferometric techniques.

GPS/GNSS Measurements

A geodetic GPS network (Figure 1) was established in the broader area of Nisyros in June 1997 in order to study ground deformation. It initially consisted of 21 stations and included a local reference station (17-Kos) at the northeastern part of Kos Island (Lagios et al. 2005). Another station (benchmark) was installed on Strongyli Islet in 2013. Moreover, a continuous operating GNSS station was established in Mandraki in November 2016, as well two more continuous station were established in 2023 in Nikia and Yali. Campaign measurements were performed in periodic times, with the last measuring period to be December 2023. All campaigns were made in the static mode using tripods cantered above the permanently installed benchmark at a given station. Post-processing was performed using the Bernese GPS Software, versions 5.2 (Dach et al. 2015), together with post-computed satellite orbits (available through the International GNSS Service) to improve the error estimation. Accuracies of 2 to 5mm and 4 to 8 mm were achieved for the horizontal and vertical components, respectively.

The GPS measurements during the active period (1997-1999) showed that the amplitude of the horizontal deformation ranged from 20 to 60 mm. The maximum horizontal displacement occurred between 1997 and 1998 during the peaking (1997) and subsequent high level (1998) of seismic activity. The period 1999-2002 Nisyros entered a different mode of deformation with a clear westward in-crease of the horizontal component in almost all its western part for the period 2001-2002. Vertical deformation in the sense of a general uplift of the whole island occurred over almost the entire active period of observation up to 2002, and in particular the majority of stations exhibited uplifts of 40 to 60 mm between 1997 and 1998. Greater values of uplift were measured at stations installed on the western uplifted side of the activated Mandraki Fault.

The GPS network on Nisyros after 2002 was re-measured in August 2012, which was a decade after its establishment. Through this decade (2002-2012), there was no significant seismic activity in the broader area, nor was there any other type of volcanic activity as would be detected via temperature increase in the fumaroles. It may thus be assumed that the ground deformation that occurred in the island was of an almost linear character without any strong fluctuations. After 2012, the network was re-measured more often, in total eight times up to 2023, deducing a more accurate velocity field of the area (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Vertical (left panel) and horizontal (right panel) deformation on Yali-Nisyros for the period 2002-2023 (relative to ITRF2014 reference frame, subtracting the regional motion of the area).

As can be seen on the velocity map for the period 2002-2023 (Figure 2), the most prominent aspect of ground deformation is the subsidence that took place in Nisyros and Yali during this ,ore than 20 years period. The subsidence reached values of more than 10mm/yr in the northern part of Nisyros, but with smaller values (~3-5 mm/yr.) in the southern and eastern parts. The horizontal velocity vectors of the stations located on the NE had motion to the SW, while the stations on the NW exhibited motion to the ENE. The amplitudes of the horizontal velocity vectors are slightly higher for the stations at the northeastern part (~9 mm/yr.) as compared to the northwestern part (~5 mm/yr.). The two GPS stations located in Lakki Plain also subsided. Generally, it should be noticed that the stations located outside the caldera's rim had exhibited stronger deformation as compared to those located inside the rim for both horizontal and vertical components. The nearly opposite direction of horizontal motion that is observed for the stations located at the eastern and western parts of Nisyros may be due to the strong subsidence which had taken place at its northern and central parts during this period, thus forcing the facing eastern and western flanks of the island to 'collapse' towards its centre which produced the observed westward and eastward horizontal motions, respectively.

Significant subsidence (~8 mm/yr.) had also occurred in Yali islet. The horizontal velocity components of the two stations, located on the extreme eastern and western parts, have similar amplitudes (~8 mm/yr.) and clearly point towards the central area of the islet. It is concluded that strong subsidence likely occurred in the region between Yali and Nisyros which caused the two edges of the islet to converge toward this area, consistent with the deformational pattern observed at those two stations.

SAR Interferometry

Conventional Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Interferometry (InSAR) and GPS measurements are the most widely used techniques to measure the ground deformation in volcanoes. For the period 2003-2010 ASAR ENVISAT images were processed in ascending and descending orbital geometry using the SqueeSAR™ Technique. Based on this technique Line of Sight (LOS) velocity maps were produced (Figure 3).

Figure 3. LOS Velocity Field deduced from the SqueeSAR™ for Ascending (left panel), and Descending (right panel) orbital geometries, for the period 2003-2010. Red and blue arrows indicate the orbit and acquisition directions for the ascending and the descending data sets, respectively.

Greater negative LOS velocities (~2.5 mm/yr) are observed along the F3 faulting system and between F1 and F2 faulting zones inside the caldera in the ascending image. These values are not observed in the descending image. The western part of Nisyros and west of the caldera's rim show similar velocities for both images, ranging from relatively stable to slightly positive values (~1.5 mm/yr). The greatest LOS velocities (1.8 to 3.0 mm/yr) are observed in the ascending image near the two small peninsulas at the extreme southwestern part, bounded by F1 and F6 faulting systems. The southeastern part of Nisyros shows small negative LOS velocities (~-1.5 mm/yr) in the ascending image and positive values (up to 2 mm/yr) in the descending image, indicating an eastward component of ground deformation during 2003-2010. The northeastern part of Nisyros has positive LOS velocities (0.6 to 1.8 mm/yr) on both images, with an inconsistent pattern of ground deformation in the northern part due to dense vegetation. The Yali islet shows no consistent deformation pattern between acquisition geometries, except in the northeastern part with relatively stable to small negative LOS velocities. Differential motion between the northeastern and southwestern parts may be due to differing geological characteristics: obsidian in

the northeast and pumices in the southwest.

For the period 2018-2022 interferometric results were obtained by the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS, <https://egms.land.copernicus.eu/>). The data of Ascending and Descending orbital geometries were initially calibrated using the permanent station in Mandraki, and then decomposed on East-West and Vertical component (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Vertical (left panel) and East-West (right panel) velocity field calibrated using the continuous GNSS station in Mandraki area.

The local calibrated and decomposed EGMS interferometric product show small velocities values for both components, indicative of linear type of deformation. The vertical velocity field highlights and confirm the velocity field deduced by the GPS technique, showing intense subsiding motion in the central and northern part of island (up to -17 mm/yr), but smaller subsidence in the southern Nisyros. The East-West component also clearly depicts the diametrical opposition between the eastern and western part of Nisyros and Yali. The western part exhibits positive velocity values, consistent to eastward motion, while the eastern flanks show negative velocities, indicative of westward motions. A feature that rises observing the East-West velocity field is that changes on the sign of motion coincide with the main tectonic zones that cross-cut the island.

Discussion

During the "unrest" period from 1996 to 2000, strong ground non-linear deformation was observed, which was explained using a model that included two MOGI Point Sources: one offshore and one inland. Interferometric results (SqueeSAR™) for the subsequent period from 2003 to 2010 showed linear deformation along major faulting zones that cross-cut the island. This deformation included a significant vertical component (subsidence) mainly in the central and northern parts, and a considerable horizontal component in the eastern, western, and southeastern parts. Differential GPS measurements for the period from 2002 to 2023, and interferometric products for the period 2018-2022 indicated intense subsidence at all stations, with a horizontal component pointing towards the central part of Nisyros. The observed deformation may be explained as a result of combined volcanic and tectonic activity, including a decrease in pressure in the possible magma chambers beneath and offshore of Nisyros Island, and possible tectonic motions along the trough offshore north of Nisyros and south of Yali Islet. Notably, there was an absence of any significant shallow seismic activity during the period from 2002 to 2023 in the vicinity of Nisyros.

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